

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PREVENTION OF RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM: CURRENT SITUATION AND THREATS

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Abstract

The present article covers the subject of terrorism, nowadays seriously affecting world countries, and its consequences. Studying the causes of terrorism, the use of the religious factor is emphasized as an instrument in the violation of stability and occurrence of confrontations in most world countries. The article as well contains information about the deaths of hundreds of thousands of people, the destruction of many residential buildings, schools and historical monuments as a result of terrorist attacks in different countries. This article provides information on the events taking place in Azerbaijan in the religious sphere during the early years of its independence, it is stressed that Azerbaijan was one of the countries most affected by terrorism. In the conclusion, the article tells in detail about the work done by Azerbaijan in the field of counter-terrorism, and the changes and additions made to the legislation.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, world, religion, stability, information, history, terrorism.

In modern times, many countries around the world suffer from religious extremism and terrorism. In many parts of the world, social stability is violated, civil conflict arises, millions of people live the life as refugees and internally displaced persons, historical architecture monuments, schools and hospitals are destroyed due to the terrorism acts.

Events happening in the regional and global environment in recent years, shows that, religions carrying the mission of promotion of high moral values, ensurance of people's unity and equality and protection of peace and tranquillity, are broadly used for implementation of political objectives and insidious plans. At present, in the world, particularly in Muslim countries, the religious factor plays a special role in the destabilization and international forces abuse it skilfully. It manifests itself in the example of numerous movements created by certain individuals and entities [1, 267].

The emergence of radicalism and extremism has different objective and subjective reasons and manifests itself in many fields. Discrimination in the state policy, exacerbation of interfaith relations, insulting of religious values in some cases and provoking of conflict and hostility based on religion are caused by these reasons [2, 72].

Meanwhile, free propagation of dangerous religious sects in some countries, lack of efficient fight against radical and extremist groups, creation of conditions for the use of religion for political purposes, unresolved international and regional conflicts for many years, and the emergence of new conflicts increases extremism and intolerance trends and expands the scope of them in the world. The efforts and measures of the world countries and international organizations in order to prevent these risks have no significant results in some cases, but causes tension on relations, complication on the situation and the increase of the conflicts.

It triggers hostility, extremism and radicalism trends, armed and bloody conflicts, innocent people to become victims of the conflict. In modern times, the

prevention of such problems seems impossible in the absence of joint efforts of state and civil society and international organizations. For efficient struggle against extremism and radicalism, strong state and civil societies are essential.

A serious threat to mankind -terrorism and extremism dates back to the ancient times and emergence of them is linked to a variety of reasons. In many cases, these conflicts are happening due to the ethnic, religious, racial and other reasons. Regardless of the motive and reasons of occurrence, terrorism is one of the manifestation forms of extremism and eliminating the threat is one of the main and important tasks of mankind.

Today, no one and no country have been guaranteed from terrorist attacks. In modern times, the peoples of the whole world, many countries from the Far South-East Asia to the Middle East, from Africa, Europe to America, feel terrible consequences of terrorism directly or indirectly and suffer from such incidents. This is a problem not only of any countries and people, but also of all mankind. Each year, hundreds of thousands of innocent people are becoming victims of terrorism as a result of the terrorism acts and political conflicts happening in different countries.

Today, in some cases, we witness emphasizing of religious factor as a reason of terrorism acts. Some bodies blame heavenly religions, which aim to bring peace, tranquillity to people, at paving the way for terrorism. In this issue, Islam is more exposed to injustice and criticism. Unfortunately, sometimes, hundreds of thousands of people think wrongly about Islam due to the unawareness, biased propaganda, inadequate behaviour of some Muslims in some cases and other reasons. In fact, no religion justifies violence, terror and religious discrimination. Since it was found, Islam has considered to respect the members of other religions important and contributed to the members of different religions to live according to their beliefs. Today, hard

stance against terrorism belongs to Islam, however, mainly, Muslims suffer from it [3, 308].

Azerbaijani people are deeply aware of the grave results and pain of terrorism as they have been exposed to terrorism in different stages of history. Unfortunately, a number of states and international organizations approach to conflicts in the region and the world with double standard, do not demonstrate a principal position and consider the solution of problems as a duty of parties involved in the conflict directly. It also approves itself in the approach toward the solution of Nagorno-Karabakh conflict which is extremely important for our country. Such subjective factors play a major role at not solving of Nagorno-Karabakh conflict to present [4, 129].

Support to terrorism at the state level, the presence at terrorism acts against Azerbaijan, killing a number of citizens of Azerbaijan and the destruction of cultural monuments by Armenia are undeniable facts. Committing a number of terrorism acts in our country at different times by Armenian special service bodies confirms this view once again [3, 311].

Abovementioned conflict began with the attempt of territorial claims to Azerbaijan and seizure of Nagorno-Karabakh by Armenia in 1988 and caused the war between two countries. In subsequent years, with the support of some foreign countries, Armenian armed forces have occupied 20 percent of Azerbaijan's territory, destroyed historical monuments, mosques, cemeteries, schools, hospitals, cultural houses, museums, and forced more than one million citizens of Azerbaijan to live in extremely difficult conditions by leaving their homelands [5, 18].

As a country experienced the pain of terrorism, Azerbaijan condemns all manifestations of terrorism, fully supports the efforts to prevent terrorist attacks, and collaborates regularly and closely with many countries and international organizations in the world in order to prevent and eliminate the reasons of this problem.

As Azerbaijan is situated in the vulnerable area where the interests of the great powers clash, the prevention of future conflict impeded to the sustainable development, and implementation of preventive measures are especially important.

In modern times, providing of freedom of conscience and religion belonging to the fundamental human rights plays a special role in the policy and mutual relations of many countries and international organizations. Today, approaching to the religious issues not only through the prism of human rights and moral values, but also as a security issue is the state's commitment and prerogative. Although religion is separated from the state, the state is responsible for the security of citizens and the religious situation in the country [6, 191].

In the Republic of Azerbaijan, the threat of religious extremism began to appear from the 90s of the last century, in the early years of independence, the country's political instability, armed conflict with Armenia and difficulties of economic situation made a lot of problems in the country. In our country where Soviet regime had been propagating atheism for more than

seventy years and activities of the religious figures and religious enlightenment were banned, the religious problems were obvious and a large part of the population's unawareness about religion, the lack of knowledge about philosophy, date, characteristics of religions created favourable conditions for the spread of radical religious sects [7, 114].

At the same time, in the early years of independence, state control in this area was weak and various organizations coming to our country to provide humanitarian assistance, tried to carry out active religious propaganda, to spread harmful religious trainings, and to influence especially the young people. The aim of these attempts was not only religious enlightenment, but it paved the way to create religious extremist groups. These organizations which wanted to win the confidence of the population, to increase the number of supporters and thereby to be able to interfere to the state policy, were concerned for changing religious activity towards their own interests. For this, they tried to take advantage of all opportunities. However, thanks to very determined and preventive measures taken by the government, the activities of these organizations were suppressed, and dangerous ideas were not allowed to spread to the community.

The recent processes happening in the world show that the easiest way for separation of any country is to involve that country in an ethnic or religious conflict. In this regard, it is alleged that the rights of ethnic minorities living in the same country are violated, ethnic groups are instigated to conflict with each other and to protest against the government [8, 195]. Therefore, in those years separatist tendencies significantly strengthened in Azerbaijan and the country faced with the threat of separation and collapse. Local and foreign forces attempted to use the ethnic groups for their political purposes and to provoke them to protest against the government and to create ethnic conflicts in the northern and southern regions of the country.

Thanks to the consistent and purposeful measures undertaken by the Azerbaijani government upon National Leader Heydar Aliyev's return to power those attempts were prevented, this field was paid more attention, and the representatives of all nations united around the idea of single Azerbaijanism.

In present time, various methods are used for the struggle against terrorism and extremism, in some cases, administrative methods are preferred. Today, one of the most effective methods of combating extremism is strengthening of public awareness and improvement of the religious knowledge of the people, especially of the young generation. General studies show that the youth are exposed to these effects mostly due to lack of religious knowledge and illiteracy. Therefore, it is very crucial to improve the quality of education at the religious educational institutions, to strengthen material-technical base, to teach secular subjects besides religious lessons, to develop comprehensive and expressive textbooks, to organize the education process based on general principles, but not on sectarianism, to avoid superstition and to form patriotism in the youth.

Today, our state successfully proceeds to take measures regarding prevention of religious extremism,

protection of our citizens from external influences, provision of stability of the religious situation in the country, and ensuring of public safety. The legal framework is being improved on a regular basis for the purposes of conformance of the normative legal acts to the international standards, determination of the rights and obligations of both government and religious organizations and restriction of the actions of the sects and movements which propagate harmful thoughts contrary to humanist principles.

One of the measures taken in this regard was several additions and amendments to the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Freedom of Religious Belief" in 2015 in order to prevent designation of the youth who received religious education abroad and were exposed to harmful religious influences, to the position of religious leader in the mosques. In accordance with the Article 21, Paragraph 3 of the above-mentioned Law "religious rites and rituals of Islam should be carried out only by citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan studied in Azerbaijan. The citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan who studied abroad, are prohibited to perform Islamic rituals" [9, page 74]. The main purpose hereof is to prevent the persons who studied abroad and were exposed to harmful ideological influences to work as a religious figure in the country and to carry out religious propaganda in the places of worship and among the people.

The provisions related to strengthening of the struggle against extremism and prevention of radical trends, have also been specified in the Laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Articles 12.1, 279.1 (Creation of armed formations or groups, which are not provided by the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and also participation in their creation and activity, supplying them by weapon, ammunition, explosives, military engineering or military equipment), 28, 283-1.3 and 283-1.3 (Involvement of citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan or stateless persons permanently residing in the Republic of Azerbaijan, to armed conflicts outside the Republic of Azerbaijan with a purpose to disseminate religious teachings under the pretence of performing religious rites or due to religious hatred or conducting military exercises for this purpose, or creation of stable group for this purpose and management of such group, participation in or preparation for those groups,

exercises or armed conflicts) of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan have particular importance in the fight against extremism [9, 188].

Azerbaijan adopted a law "On fight against religious extremism" in December 2015. Adoption of this Law have made significant contributions to the prevention of ethnic, social or religious hatred, humiliation of national dignity, restriction of the citizens' rights or determination of priorities due to their nationality, race, social or religious affiliations.

Today, the law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Azerbaijan implement consistent and systematic measures to prevent extremism and radical trends in the country. Prevention of the activities of radical sects in our country, measures taken against the youth combating in the armed groups operating abroad, and their arrest while returning the country confirm this view once again.

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